

Article

Remarkable Classes of Almost 3-Contact Metric Manifolds

Giulia Dileo

Department of Mathematics, University of Bari Aldo Moro, Via E. Orabona 4, 70125 Bari, Italy; giulia.dileo@uniba.it

Abstract: We introduce a new class of almost 3-contact metric manifolds, called 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds. We show fundamental geometric properties of these manifolds, analyzing analogies and differences with the known classes of 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki ($\alpha \neq 0$) and 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds.

Keywords: almost 3-contact metric manifold; 3-Sasaki; 3-cosymplectic; 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki; 3- δ -cosymplectic; metric connection with skew torsion

MSC: 53C15; 53C25; 53B05

1. Introduction

An almost 3-contact metric manifold is a $(4n + 3)$ -dimensional differentiable manifold M endowed with three almost contact metric structures $(\varphi, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, sharing the same Riemannian metric g and satisfying suitable compatibility conditions, equivalent to the existence of a sphere of almost contact metric structures. In the recent paper [1], new classes of almost 3-contact metric manifolds were introduced and studied. The first remarkable class is given by 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki manifolds defined as almost 3-contact metric manifolds $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ such that

$$d\eta_i = 2\alpha\Phi_i + 2(\alpha - \delta)\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^*, \delta \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1)$$

for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$. This is a generalization of 3-Sasaki manifolds, which correspond to the values $\alpha = \delta = 1$. A second class introduced in [1] is given by 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds defined by the conditions

$$d\eta_i = -2\delta\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \quad d\Phi_i = 0, \quad \delta \in \mathbb{R},$$

generalizing 3-cosymplectic manifolds which correspond to the value $\delta = 0$.

In the present paper we will introduce a third class of almost 3-contact metric manifolds, which is in fact a second (and alternative) generalization of 3-cosymplectic manifolds. We will consider almost 3-contact metric manifolds whose structure tensor fields satisfy

$$d\eta_i = -2\delta\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \quad d\Phi_i = -2\delta(\eta_j \wedge \Phi_k - \eta_k \wedge \Phi_j), \quad \delta \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$. When $\delta = 0$ we recover a 3-cosymplectic manifold. We will call these manifolds 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds. The choice of name is due to the fact that for a 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki manifold, Equation (1) implies

$$d\Phi_i = 2(\alpha - \delta)(\eta_j \wedge \Phi_k - \eta_k \wedge \Phi_j), \quad (3)$$

so that the two equations in (2) formally correspond to (1) and (3) with $\alpha = 0$, although in this case the second equation is no more a consequence of the first one. In fact the two conditions in (2) are not completely independent (see Remark 1). Examples of 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki structures can be defined on the semidirect products $SO(3) \ltimes \mathbb{R}^{4n}$. The structure on these Lie groups was introduced in [2] as an example of canonical abelian almost 3-contact

Citation: Dileo, G. Remarkable Classes of Almost 3-Contact Metric Manifolds. *Axioms* **2021**, *10*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms10010008>

Received: 9 December 2020
Accepted: 7 January 2021
Published: 11 January 2021

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2021 by the author. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

metric structure. It is also shown in [2] that the Lie group $SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^{4n}$ admits co-compact discrete subgroups, so that the corresponding compact quotients admit almost 3-contact metric structures of the same type.

One can show that for all the above three classes of manifolds, 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki, 3- δ -cosymplectic, and 3- $(0, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds, the structure is hypernormal, the characteristic vector fields $\xi_i, i = 1, 2, 3$, are Killing and they span an integrable distribution, called vertical, with totally geodesic leaves. Nevertheless, there are remarkable geometric differences between the three classes. In the 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki case the 1-forms η_i are all contact forms, i.e., $\eta_i \wedge (d\eta_i)^n \neq 0$ everywhere on M , while for the other two classes, the horizontal distribution defined by $\eta_i = 0, i = 1, 2, 3$, is integrable. Both 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds and 3- $(0, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds are locally isometric to the Riemannian product of a 3-dimensional Lie group, tangent to the vertical distribution, and a $4n$ -dimensional manifold tangent to the horizontal distribution. The Lie group is either isomorphic to $SO(3)$ or flat depending on whether $\delta \neq 0$ or $\delta = 0$. Each horizontal leaf is endowed with a hyper-Kähler structure. The difference between 3- δ -cosymplectic and 3- $(0, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds lies in the projectability of the structure tensor fields $\varphi_i, i = 1, 2, 3$, with respect to the vertical foliation. They are always projectable for 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds, but not for 3- $(0, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds with $\delta \neq 0$. In this case one can project a transverse quaternionic structure, as it happens for 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki manifolds. Finally, for the three classes of manifolds, we analyze the existence of a canonical metric connection with totally skew-symmetric torsion.

2. Almost Contact and Almost 3-Contact Metric Manifolds

An *almost contact manifold* is a smooth manifold M of dimension $2n + 1$, endowed with a structure (φ, ξ, η) , where φ is a $(1, 1)$ -tensor field, ξ a vector field, and η a 1-form such that

$$\varphi^2 = -I + \eta \otimes \xi, \quad \eta(\xi) = 1,$$

implying that $\varphi\xi = 0, \eta \circ \varphi = 0$, and φ has rank $2n$. The tangent bundle of M splits as $TM = \mathcal{H} \oplus \langle \xi \rangle$, where \mathcal{H} is the $2n$ -dimensional distribution defined by $\mathcal{H} = \text{Im}(\varphi) = \text{Ker}(\eta)$. The vector field ξ is called the *characteristic* or *Reeb vector field*.

On the product manifold $M \times \mathbb{R}$ one can define an almost complex structure J by $J\left(X, f \frac{d}{dt}\right) = \left(\varphi X - f\xi, \eta(X) \frac{d}{dt}\right)$, where X is a vector field tangent to M, t is the coordinate of \mathbb{R} and f is a C^∞ function on $M \times \mathbb{R}$. If J is integrable, the almost contact structure is said to be *normal* and this is equivalent to the vanishing of the tensor field $N_\varphi := [\varphi, \varphi] + d\eta \otimes \xi$, where $[\varphi, \varphi]$ is the Nijenhuis torsion of φ [3]. More precisely, for any vector fields X and Y, N_φ is given by

$$N_\varphi(X, Y) = [\varphi X, \varphi Y] + \varphi^2[X, Y] - \varphi[\varphi X, Y] - \varphi[X, \varphi Y] + d\eta(X, Y)\xi. \tag{4}$$

It is known that any almost contact manifold admits a compatible metric, that is a Riemannian metric g such that $g(\varphi X, \varphi Y) = g(X, Y) - \eta(X)\eta(Y)$ for every $X, Y \in \mathfrak{X}(M)$. Then $\eta = g(\cdot, \xi)$ and $\mathcal{H} = \langle \xi \rangle^\perp$. The manifold $(M, \varphi, \xi, \eta, g)$ is called an *almost contact metric manifold*. The associated fundamental 2-form is defined by $\Phi(X, Y) = g(X, \varphi Y)$.

We recall some remarkable classes of almost contact metric manifolds.

- An α -*contact metric manifold* is defined as an almost contact metric manifold such that

$$d\eta = 2\alpha\Phi, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^*,$$

When $\alpha = 1$, it is called a *contact metric manifold*; the 1-form η is a *contact form*, that is $\eta \wedge (d\eta)^n \neq 0$ everywhere on M . An α -*Sasaki manifold* is a normal α -contact metric manifold, and again such a manifold with $\alpha = 1$ is called a *Sasaki manifold*.

- An *almost cosymplectic manifold* is defined as an almost contact metric manifold such that

$$d\eta = 0, \quad d\Phi = 0;$$

if furthermore the structure is normal, M is called a *cosymplectic manifold*. It is worth remarking that some authors call these manifolds *almost coKähler* and *coKähler*, respectively ([4]).

- A *quasi-Sasaki manifold* is a normal almost contact metric manifold with closed 2-form Φ . This class includes both α -Sasaki and cosymplectic manifolds. The Reeb vector field of a quasi-Sasaki manifold is always Killing.

Both α -Sasaki manifolds and cosymplectic manifolds can be characterized by means of the Levi-Civita connection ∇^g . Indeed, one can show that an almost contact metric manifold $(M, \varphi, \xi, \eta, g)$ is α -Sasaki if and only if

$$(\nabla_X^g \varphi)Y = \alpha(g(X, Y)\xi - \eta(X)Y) \quad \forall X, Y \in \mathfrak{X}(M).$$

An almost contact metric manifold is cosymplectic if and only if $\nabla^g \varphi = 0$; further, this is equivalent to requiring the manifold to be locally isometric to the Riemannian product of a real line (tangent to the Reeb vector field) and a Kähler manifold.

For a comprehensive introduction to almost contact metric manifolds we refer to [3]. For Sasaki geometry, we also recommend the monograph [5]; the survey [4] covers fundamental properties and recent results on cosymplectic geometry.

An *almost 3-contact manifold* is a differentiable manifold M of dimension $4n + 3$ endowed with three almost contact structures $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i), i = 1, 2, 3$, satisfying the following relations,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_k &= \varphi_i \varphi_j - \eta_j \otimes \xi_i = -\varphi_j \varphi_i + \eta_i \otimes \xi_j, \\ \xi_k &= \varphi_i \xi_j = -\varphi_j \xi_i, \quad \eta_k = \eta_i \circ \varphi_j = -\eta_j \circ \varphi_i, \end{aligned}$$

for any even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$ ([3]). The tangent bundle of M splits as $TM = \mathcal{H} \oplus \mathcal{V}$, where

$$\mathcal{H} := \bigcap_{i=1}^3 \text{Ker}(\eta_i), \quad \mathcal{V} := \langle \xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3 \rangle.$$

In particular, \mathcal{H} has rank $4n$. We call any vector belonging to the distribution \mathcal{H} *horizontal* and any vector belonging to the distribution \mathcal{V} *vertical*. The manifold is said to be *hypernormal* if each almost contact structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i)$ is normal. In [6] it was proved that if two of the almost contact structures are normal, then so is the third.

The existence of an almost 3-contact structure is equivalent to the existence of a sphere $\{(\varphi_x, \xi_x, \eta_x)\}_{x \in S^2}$ of almost contact structures such that

$$\varphi_x \circ \varphi_y - \eta_y \otimes \xi_x = \varphi_{x \times y} - (x \cdot y)I, \quad \varphi_x \xi_y = \xi_{x \times y}, \quad \eta_x \circ \varphi_y = \eta_{x \times y},$$

for every $x, y \in S^2$, where \cdot and \times denote the standard inner product and cross product on \mathbb{R}^3 . In fact, if the structure is hypernormal, then every structure in the sphere is normal ([7]).

Any almost 3-contact manifold admits a Riemannian metric g which is compatible with each of the three structures. Then M is said to be an *almost 3-contact metric manifold* with structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g), i = 1, 2, 3$. For ease of notation, we will denote an almost 3-contact metric manifold by $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$, omitting $i = 1, 2, 3$. The subbundles \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{V} are orthogonal with respect to g and the three Reeb vector fields ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 are orthonormal. In fact, the structure group of the tangent bundle is reducible to $\text{Sp}(n) \times \{1\}$ [8].

Given an almost 3-contact metric structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$, an \mathcal{H} -homothetic deformation is defined by

$$\eta'_i = c\eta_i, \quad \xi'_i = \frac{1}{c}\xi_i, \quad \varphi'_i = \varphi_i, \quad g' = ag + b \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \otimes \eta_i, \quad (5)$$

where a, b, c are real numbers such that $a > 0, c^2 = a + b > 0$, ensuring that $(\varphi'_i, \xi'_i, \eta'_i, g')$ is an almost 3-contact metric structure. In particular, the fundamental 2-forms Φ_i and Φ'_i associated to the structures are related by

$$\Phi'_i = a\Phi_i - b\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \tag{6}$$

where (i, j, k) is an even permutation of $(1, 2, 3)$.

An almost 3-contact metric manifold is called

- 3- α -Sasaki, with $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^*$, if $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is α -Sasaki for all $i = 1, 2, 3$, i.e. the structure is hypernormal and

$$d\eta_i = 2\alpha\Phi_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3; \tag{7}$$

when $\alpha = 1$, it is a 3-Sasaki manifold;

- 3-cosymplectic if $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is cosymplectic for all $i = 1, 2, 3$, i.e. the structure is hypernormal and

$$d\eta_i = 0, \quad d\Phi_i = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3; \tag{8}$$

- 3-quasi-Sasaki manifold if each structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is quasi-Sasaki; this class includes both 3- α -Sasaki and 3-cosymplectic manifolds.

These classes were deeply investigated by various authors. See [5,9,10] and references therein for 3-Sasakian geometry, the papers [7,11,12] for 3-cosymplectic manifolds, and [13,14] for 3-quasi-Sasaki manifolds.

In fact, both for 3-Sasaki and 3-cosymplectic manifolds, the hypernormality is consequence of the structure Equations (7) and (8) respectively. This was proved by Kashiwada in [15] for 3-Sasaki manifolds, and in ([16], Theorem 4.13) for 3-cosymplectic manifolds.

In [1] the new classes of 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki manifolds and 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds were introduced, generalizing the classes of 3- α -Sasaki and 3-cosymplectic manifolds, respectively. We will review the definitions and the basic properties of these manifolds in the next section. For both these two classes the hypernormality is a consequence of the defining structure equations for the manifolds, thus generalizing the analogous results for 3-Sasaki and 3-cosymplectic manifolds. This is obtained by using the following Lemma:

Lemma 1 ([1]). *Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be an almost 3-contact metric manifold. Then the following formula holds $\forall X, Y, Z \in \mathfrak{X}(M)$:*

$$\begin{aligned} g(N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y), Z) &= \\ &= -d\Phi_j(X, Y, \varphi_j Z) + d\Phi_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_j Z) + d\Phi_k(X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_j Z) + d\Phi_k(\varphi_i X, Y, \varphi_j Z) \\ &\quad - \eta_i(X)[d\eta_j(\varphi_i Y, \varphi_j Z) + d\eta_k(Y, \varphi_j Z)] + \eta_i(Y)[d\eta_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_j Z) + d\eta_k(X, \varphi_j Z)] \\ &\quad + \eta_j(Z)[d\eta_j(X, Y) - d\eta_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y)] - \eta_j(Z)[d\eta_k(X, \varphi_i Y) + d\eta_k(\varphi_i X, Y)]. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

In the following we will be concerned with various classes of almost 3-contact metric manifolds where the three Reeb vector fields are all Killing. In this case one can show that there exists a function $\delta \in C^\infty(M)$ such that

$$\eta_r([\xi_s, \xi_t]) = 2\delta\epsilon_{rst}, \quad r, s, t = 1, 2, 3$$

where ϵ_{rst} is the totally skew-symmetric symbol, or equivalently $d\eta_r(\xi_s, \xi_t) = -2\delta\epsilon_{rst}$. We call δ a Reeb commutator function, we refer to [1] for more information on this notion.

3. 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki Manifolds and 3- δ -Cosymplectic Manifolds

This section is a short review of 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki manifolds and 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds. These were discussed in detail in [1,17].

Definition 1. An almost 3-contact metric manifold $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is called a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold if it satisfies

$$d\eta_i = 2\alpha\Phi_i + 2(\alpha - \delta)\eta_j \wedge \eta_k$$

for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$, where $\alpha \neq 0$ and δ are real constants.

When $\alpha = \delta = 1$, we have a 3-contact metric manifold, and hence a 3-Sasaki manifold by Kashiwada’s theorem [15]. In the following, when considering $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds we will always mean $\alpha \neq 0$. As an immediate consequences of the definition one obtains the following properties:

1. Each ξ_i is an infinitesimal automorphism of the distribution \mathcal{H} , i. e.

$$d\eta_r(X, \xi_s) = 0 \quad X \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H}), \quad r, s = 1, 2, 3;$$

2. The constant δ is the Reeb commutator function;
3. The differentials $d\Phi_i$ are given by

$$d\Phi_i = 2(\delta - \alpha)(\eta_k \wedge \Phi_j - \eta_j \wedge \Phi_k).$$

Applying Lemma 1 one shows the following

Theorem 1 ([1], Theorem 2.2.1). Any $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is hypernormal.

In particular, a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold with $\alpha = \delta$ is $3-\alpha$ -Sasaki. It can be also shown that the vertical distribution of any $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is integrable with totally geodesic leaves and each Reeb vector field ξ_i is Killing.

We can distinguish three main classes of $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds. A $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is called *degenerate* if $\delta = 0$ and *non-degenerate* otherwise. Quaternionic Heisenberg groups are examples of degenerate $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds (see ([1], Example 2.3.2)). Considering an \mathcal{H} -homothetic deformation of a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki structure, as in (5), one can verify that the obtained structure $(\varphi', \xi', \eta', g')$ is a $3-(\alpha', \delta')$ -Sasaki with

$$\alpha' = \alpha \frac{c}{a}, \quad \delta' = \frac{\delta}{c}.$$

In particular, \mathcal{H} -homothetic deformations preserve the class of degenerate manifolds. In the nondegenerate case, one sees immediately that $\alpha' \delta'$ has the same sign as $\alpha \delta$. This justifies the distinction between *positive* $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds, with $\alpha \delta > 0$, and *negative* $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds, with $\alpha \delta < 0$. In fact, it can be shown that a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is positive if and only if it is \mathcal{H} -homothetic to a 3-Sasaki manifold, and negative if and only if it is \mathcal{H} -homothetic to a $3-(\alpha', \delta')$ -Sasaki manifold with $\alpha' = -1, \delta' = 1$.

Examples of negative $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds can be obtained in the following way. It is known that quaternionic Kähler (not hyper-Kähler) manifolds with negative scalar curvature admit a canonically associated principal $SO(3)$ -bundle $P(M)$ which is endowed with a *negative 3-Sasaki structure* [18,19]. This is a 3-structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, \tilde{g})$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, where $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i)$ is a normal almost 3-contact structure, and \tilde{g} is a compatible semi-Riemannian metric, with signature $(3, 4n)$, where $4n$ is the dimension of the base space, and $d\eta_i(X, Y) = 2\tilde{g}(X, \varphi_i Y)$. Then, one can define the Riemannian metric

$$g = -\tilde{g} + 2 \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \otimes \eta_i,$$

which is compatible with the structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i)$, and satisfies $d\eta_i = -2\Phi_i - 4\eta_j \wedge \eta_k$, where $\Phi_i(X, Y) = g(X, \varphi_i Y)$ (see also [19]). Therefore $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki structure with $\alpha = -1$ and $\delta = 1$.

The following Theorem regarding the transverse geometry with respect to the vertical foliation of a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is proved in [17]:

Theorem 2. Any $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold M admits a locally defined Riemannian submersion $\pi: M \rightarrow N$ along its horizontal distribution \mathcal{H} such that N carries a quaternionic Kähler structure given by

$$\check{\varphi}_i = \pi_* \circ \varphi_i \circ s_*, \quad i = 1, 2, 3,$$

where $s: U \rightarrow M$ is any local smooth section of the Riemannian submersion. The covariant derivatives of the almost complex structures $\check{\varphi}_i$ are given by

$$\nabla_X^{\check{\varphi}_i} \check{\varphi}_i = 2\delta(\check{\eta}_k(X)\check{\varphi}_j - \check{\eta}_j(X)\check{\varphi}_k)$$

where $\check{\eta}_i(X) = \eta_i(s_*X) \circ s$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. The scalar curvature of the base space N is $16n(n + 2)\alpha\delta$.

The Riemannian Ricci tensor of any $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is computed in [1]:

$$\text{Ric}^\delta = 2\alpha(2\delta(n + 2) - 3\alpha)g + 2(\alpha - \delta)((2n + 3)\alpha - \delta) \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \otimes \eta_i. \tag{10}$$

In particular, a $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold is Riemannian Einstein if and only if $\delta = \alpha$, in which case the structure is $3-\alpha$ -Sasaki, or $\delta = (2n + 3)\alpha$.

Notice that, by Theorem 2, a non-degenerate $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifold locally fibers over a quaternionic Kähler space of positive or negative scalar curvature, according to $\alpha\delta > 0$ or $\alpha\delta < 0$, respectively. In [17] a systematic study of homogeneous non-degenerate $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds has been carried out, obtaining a complete classification in the positive case, where the base space of the homogeneous fibration turns out to be a symmetric Wolf space. In the case $\alpha\delta < 0$, one can provide a general construction of homogeneous $3-(\alpha, \delta)$ -Sasaki manifolds fibering over nonsymmetric Alekseevsky spaces.

We recall now the definition and some basic facts on $3-\delta$ -cosymplectic manifolds.

Definition 2. A $3-\delta$ -cosymplectic manifold is an almost 3-contact metric manifold satisfying

$$d\eta_i = -2\delta\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \quad d\Phi_i = 0,$$

for some $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$ and for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$.

When $\delta = 0$, the fact that the forms η_i and Φ_i are all closed implies that the structure is hypernormal ([16], Theorem 4.13). In fact this immediately follows from (9). Therefore, a $3-\delta$ -cosymplectic manifold with $\delta = 0$ is 3-cosymplectic. In particular, it is 3-quasi-Sasaki and the Reeb vector fields are all Killing. The local structure of these manifolds is described by the following:

Proposition 1 ([12]). Any 3-cosymplectic manifold of dimension $4n + 3$ is locally the Riemannian product of a hyper-Kähler manifold of dimension $4n$ and a 3-dimensional flat abelian Lie group.

As a consequence, since every hyper-Kähler manifold is Ricci flat, even the Riemannian Ricci tensor of any 3-cosymplectic manifold vanishes.

As regards $3-\delta$ -cosymplectic manifolds with $\delta \neq 0$, even in this case one can show that the structure is hypernormal, the Reeb vector fields are Killing, and the manifold locally decomposes as a Riemannian product [1]. In particular,

Proposition 2. Any $3-\delta$ -cosymplectic manifold with $\delta \neq 0$ is locally the Riemannian product of a hyper-Kähler manifold and a 3-dimensional Lie group isomorphic to $\text{SO}(3)$, with constant curvature δ^2 . Consequently, the Riemannian Ricci tensor is $\text{Ric}^\delta = 2\delta^2 \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \otimes \eta_i$.

In both cases, i.e., $\delta = 0$ or $\delta \neq 0$, the hyper-Kähler manifold is tangent to the horizontal distribution, while the 3-dimensional Lie group is tangent to the vertical distribution. In fact, examples of these manifolds can be obtained taking Riemannian products $N \times G$, where (N, J_i, h) , $i = 1, 2, 3$, is a hyper-Kähler manifold, and G is a 3-dimensional Lie group, which is either abelian, or isomorphic to $SO(3)$. If ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 are generators of the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} of G , satisfying $[\xi_i, \xi_j] = 2\delta\xi_k$, $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$, then one can define in a natural manner an almost 3-contact metric structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ on the product $N \times G$, setting

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_i|_{TN} &= J_i, & \varphi_i\xi_i &= 0, & \varphi_i\xi_j &= \xi_k, & \varphi_i\xi_k &= -\xi_j, \\ \eta_i|_{TN} &= 0, & \eta_i(\xi_i) &= 1, & \eta_i(\xi_j) &= \eta_i(\xi_k) &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

and g the product metric of h and the left invariant Riemannian metric on G with respect to which ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 are an orthonormal basis of \mathfrak{g} .

For a comparison with the class of 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds, which will be introduced in the next section, it is worth remarking that for a 3- δ -cosymplectic manifold $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ the Lie derivatives of the structure tensor fields φ_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$ with respect to the Reeb vector fields are given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i}\varphi_i = 0, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\xi_i}\varphi_j = 2\delta(\eta_i \otimes \xi_j - \eta_j \otimes \xi_i) = -\mathcal{L}_{\xi_j}\varphi_i \tag{11}$$

for every $i, j = 1, 2, 3$. Indeed, in a 3- δ -cosymplectic manifold the Levi-Civita connection satisfies ([1], Proposition 2.1.1):

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_i &= 0, \\ (\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_j)X &= \delta(\eta_i(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_i) = -(\nabla_{\xi_j}^g \varphi_i)X, \\ \nabla_X^g \xi_i &= \delta(\eta_k(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_k), \end{aligned}$$

where (i, j, k) is an even permutation of $(1, 2, 3)$ and $X \in \mathfrak{X}(M)$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i}\varphi_i)X &= [\xi_i, \varphi_i X] - \varphi_i[\xi_i, X] \\ &= \nabla_{\xi_i}^g(\varphi_i X) - \nabla_{\varphi_i X}^g \xi_i - \varphi_i(\nabla_{\xi_i}^g X) + \varphi_i(\nabla_X^g \xi_i) \\ &= (\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_i)X - \nabla_{\varphi_i X}^g \xi_i + \varphi_i(\nabla_X^g \xi_i) \\ &= -\delta(\eta_k(\varphi_i X)\xi_j - \eta_j(\varphi_i X)\xi_k) + \delta(\eta_k(X)\varphi_i \xi_j - \eta_j(X)\varphi_i \xi_k) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i}\varphi_j)X &= (\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_j)X - \nabla_{\varphi_i X}^g \xi_i + \varphi_j(\nabla_X^g \xi_i) \\ &= \delta(\eta_i(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_i) - \delta\eta_k(\varphi_j X)\xi_j - \delta\eta_j(X)\varphi_j \xi_k \\ &= 2\delta(\eta_i(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_i) = -(\mathcal{L}_{\xi_j}\varphi_i)X. \end{aligned}$$

4. 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki Manifolds

In this section we introduce the class of 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds.

Definition 3. An almost 3-contact metric manifold $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ will be called 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold if

$$d\eta_i = -2\delta\eta_j \wedge \eta_k, \quad d\Phi_i = -2\delta(\eta_j \wedge \Phi_k - \eta_k \wedge \Phi_j) \tag{12}$$

for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$, and for some real constant $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$.

In particular, the structure is not 3-quasi-Sasaki when $\delta \neq 0$, and we have the following basic properties for a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold:

1. The horizontal distribution \mathcal{H} is integrable;

2. Each ξ_i is an infinitesimal automorphism of the distribution \mathcal{H} , i. e.

$$d\eta_r(X, \xi_s) = 0 \quad X \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H}), \quad r, s = 1, 2, 3;$$

3. The constant δ is the Reeb commutator function.

Remark 1. In case $\delta \neq 0$, the two equations in (12) are not completely independent. Indeed, if one assumes $d\Phi_i = -2\gamma(\eta_j \wedge \Phi_k - \eta_k \wedge \Phi_j)$, $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^*$, differentiating this equation, and combining with $d\eta_i = -2\delta\eta_j \wedge \eta_k$, a straightforward computation gives $\gamma = \delta$. Thus, there is no freedom for the choice of constant in the second equation.

If $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ is a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki structure, applying an \mathcal{H} -homothetic deformation as in (5), an easy computation using (6) shows that the new structure $(\varphi'_i, \eta'_i, \xi'_i, g')$ is again 3-(0, δ')-Sasaki, with $\delta' = \frac{\delta}{c}$.

Example 1. Consider the abelian Lie algebra \mathbb{R}^{4n} spanned by vectors $v_r, v_{n+r}, v_{2n+r}, v_{3n+r}, \dots, v_{(n-1)n+r}$, and endowed with the hypercomplex structure $\{J_1, J_2, J_3\}$ defined by

$$J_i(v_r) = v_{in+r}, \quad J_i(v_{in+r}) = -v_r, \quad J_i(v_{jn+r}) = v_{kn+r}, \quad J_i(v_{kn+r}) = -v_{jn+r},$$

for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$. Let us consider also the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{so}(3)$ spanned by ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 with Lie brackets given by $[\xi_i, \xi_j] = 2\delta\xi_k$, $\delta \neq 0$. Let ρ be the representation of $\mathfrak{so}(3)$ on \mathbb{R}^{4n} given by

$$\rho : \mathfrak{so}(3) \rightarrow \mathfrak{gl}(4n, \mathbb{R}), \quad \rho(\xi_i) = \delta J_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

On the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{so}(3) \times_{\rho} \mathbb{R}^{4n}$ on can define in a natural way an almost 3-contact metric structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$, with

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_i|_{\mathbb{R}^{4n}} &= J_i, & \varphi_i(\xi_i) &= 0, & \varphi_i(\xi_j) &= \xi_k = -\varphi_j(\xi_k), \\ \eta_i|_{\mathbb{R}^{4n}} &= 0, & \eta_i(\xi_i) &= 1, & \eta_i(\xi_j) &= \eta_i(\xi_k) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and where g is the inner product such that the vectors $\xi_i, v_l, i = 1, 2, 3, l = 1, \dots, 4n$ are orthonormal. In particular, the non zero brackets on \mathfrak{g} are given by

$$[\xi_i, \xi_j] = 2\delta\xi_k, \quad [\xi_i, X] = \delta\varphi_i(X), \quad X \in \mathbb{R}^{4n}.$$

The representation $\rho : \mathfrak{so}(3) \rightarrow \mathfrak{gl}(4n, \mathbb{R})$ can be integrated to a representation $\tilde{\rho} : \text{SO}(3) \rightarrow \text{GL}(4n, \mathbb{R})$. Therefore, identifying \mathbb{R}^{4n} with \mathbb{H}^n in a natural way, the simply connected Lie group $G = \text{SO}(3) \times_{\tilde{\rho}} \mathbb{H}^n$, with Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , admits a left invariant almost 3-contact metric structure $(\varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$. One can easily verify that this structure satisfies (12).

Remark 2. For more details on the above example we refer to [2], where \mathfrak{g} is described as a remarkable example of a Lie algebra endowed with an abelian almost 3-contact metric structure. In fact, the structure defined on \mathfrak{g} belongs to the class of canonical abelian structures, so that the Lie group G admits a unique metric connection with totally skew symmetric torsion ∇ such that

$$\nabla_X \varphi_i = 2\delta(\eta_k(X)\varphi_j - \eta_j(X)\varphi_k)$$

for every vector field X and for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$. The torsion of the canonical connection ∇ is $T = 2\delta\eta_1 \wedge \eta_2 \wedge \eta_3$, which satisfies $\nabla T = 0$.

It is also shown in [2] that the Lie group G admits co-compact discrete subgroups, so that the corresponding compact quotients admit almost 3-contact metric structures of the same type.

Proposition 3. Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold. Then the structure is hypernormal.

Proof. In order to compute the tensor fields N_{φ_i} , we apply Lemma 1. We always denote by X, Y, Z horizontal vector fields and by (i, j, k) an even permutation of $(1, 2, 3)$.

Being $d\Phi_i(X, Y, Z) = 0$, then $N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y, Z) = 0$ for every $i = 1, 2, 3$. Furthermore, since the horizontal distribution is integrable, by the definition of the tensor field N_{φ_i} (see (4)), one has $N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y, \xi_r) = 0$ for all $r = 1, 2, 3$. Notice that, since

$$\xi_i \lrcorner \Phi_i = 0, \quad \xi_j \lrcorner \Phi_i = -\eta_k, \quad \xi_k \lrcorner \Phi_i = \eta_j,$$

from the second equation in (12), we have,

$$\xi_i \lrcorner d\Phi_i = 0, \quad \xi_j \lrcorner d\Phi_i = -2\delta(\Phi_k + \eta_{ij}), \quad \xi_k \lrcorner d\Phi_i = 2\delta(\Phi_j + \eta_{ki}). \tag{13}$$

Therefore, from Lemma 1, applying (12) and (13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\varphi_i}(X, \xi_i, Z) &= -d\Phi_j(X, \xi_i, \varphi_j Z) + d\Phi_k(\varphi_i X, \xi_i, \varphi_j Z) + d\eta_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_j Z) + d\eta_k(X, \varphi_j Z) \\ &= -2\delta\Phi_k(\varphi_j Z, X) - 2\delta\Phi_j(\varphi_j Z, \varphi_i X) \\ &= 2\delta\Phi_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_j Z) + 2\delta\Phi_k(X, \varphi_j Z) = -2\delta g(\varphi_i X, Z) - 2\delta g(X, \varphi_i Z) = 0, \\ N_{\varphi_i}(X, \xi_j, Z) &= d\Phi_j(\varphi_i X, \xi_k, \varphi_j Z) + d\Phi_k(\varphi_i X, \xi_j, \varphi_j Z) \\ &= -2\delta\Phi_i(\varphi_j Z, \varphi_i X) + 2\delta\Phi_i(\varphi_j Z, \varphi_i X) = 0, \\ N_{\varphi_i}(X, \xi_k, Z) &= -d\Phi_j(X, \xi_k, \varphi_j Z) - d\Phi_k(X, \xi_j, \varphi_j Z) \\ &= 2\delta\Phi_i(\varphi_j Z, X) - 2\delta\Phi_i(\varphi_j Z, X) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Equations (13) implies $d\Phi_r(X, \xi_s, \xi_t) = 0$ for every $r, s, t = 1, 2, 3$ and $X \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H})$. Taking also into account that $d\eta_r(X, \xi_s) = 0$, we deduce from (9) that

$$N_{\varphi_r}(X, \xi_s, \xi_t) = N_{\varphi_r}(\xi_s, \xi_t, X) = 0.$$

Finally, (9) implies together with $d\eta_r(\xi_s, \xi_t) = -2\delta\epsilon_{rst}$ that

$$N_{\varphi_i}(\xi_i, \xi_j, \xi_k) = N_{\varphi_i}(\xi_i, \xi_k, \xi_j) = N_{\varphi_i}(\xi_j, \xi_k, \xi_i) = 0,$$

completing the proof that M is hypernormal. \square

Proposition 4. Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold. Then the Levi-Civita connection satisfies for all $X, Y \in \mathfrak{X}(M)$ and any cyclic permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$:

$$\begin{aligned} (\nabla_X^g \varphi_i)Y &= 2\delta [\eta_k(X)\varphi_j Y - \eta_j(X)\varphi_k Y] \\ &\quad - \delta [\eta_j(X)\eta_j(Y) + \eta_k(X)\eta_k(Y)]\xi_i + \delta \eta_i(Y) [\eta_j(X)\xi_j + \eta_k(X)\xi_k] \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

and

$$\nabla_X^g \xi_i = \delta (\eta_k(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_k), \tag{15}$$

$$\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \xi_i = 0, \quad \nabla_{\xi_i}^g \xi_j = -\nabla_{\xi_j}^g \xi_i = \delta \xi_k. \tag{16}$$

In particular, each ξ_i is a Killing vector field.

Proof. Since the structure is hypernormal, by ([3], Lemma 6.1), the Levi-Civita connection satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} 2g((\nabla_X^g \varphi_i)Y, Z) &= d\Phi_i(X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z) - d\Phi_i(X, Y, Z) \\ &\quad + d\eta_i(\varphi_i Y, X)\eta_i(Z) - d\eta_i(\varphi_i Z, X)\eta_i(Y). \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Further, an easy computation (see [1]) shows that for every cyclic permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_j(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y) &= -\Phi_j(X, Y) - (\eta_k \wedge \eta_i)(X, Y), \\ \Phi_k(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y) &= -\Phi_k(X, Y) - (\eta_i \wedge \eta_j)(X, Y), \\ \Phi_j(\varphi_i X, Y) &= -\Phi_k(X, Y) - \eta_i(X)\eta_j(Y), \\ \Phi_k(\varphi_i X, Y) &= \Phi_j(X, Y) - \eta_i(X)\eta_k(Y). \end{aligned}$$

Then, using the second equation in (12) and the above equations, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d\Phi_i(X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z) &= \\ &= -2\delta [\eta_j(X)\Phi_k(\varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z) + \eta_j(\varphi_i Y)\Phi_k(\varphi_i Z, X) + \eta_j(\varphi_i Z)\Phi_k(X, \varphi_i Y) \\ &\quad - \eta_k(X)\Phi_j(\varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z) - \eta_k(\varphi_i Y)\Phi_j(\varphi_i Z, X) - \eta_k(\varphi_i Z)\Phi_j(X, \varphi_i Y)] \\ &= -2\delta [-\eta_j(X)\Phi_k(Y, Z) - \eta_j(X)(\eta_i \wedge \eta_j)(Y, Z) \\ &\quad - \eta_k(Y)\Phi_j(Z, X) + \eta_k(Y)\eta_i(Z)\eta_k(X) + \eta_k(Z)\Phi_j(Y, X) - \eta_k(Z)\eta_i(Y)\eta_k(X) \\ &\quad + \eta_k(X)\Phi_j(Y, Z) + \eta_k(X)(\eta_k \wedge \eta_i)(Y, Z) \\ &\quad + \eta_j(Y)\Phi_k(Z, X) + \eta_j(Y)\eta_i(Z)\eta_j(X) - \eta_j(Z)\Phi_k(Y, X) - \eta_j(Z)\eta_i(Y)\eta_j(X)] \\ &= d\Phi_i(X, Y, Z) + 4\delta [\eta_j(X)\Phi_k(Y, Z) - \eta_k(X)\Phi_j(Y, Z)] \\ &\quad + 4\delta \eta_j(X)[\eta_i(Y)\eta_j(Z) - \eta_j(Y)\eta_i(Z)] \\ &\quad + 4\delta \eta_k(X)[\eta_i(Y)\eta_k(Z) - \eta_k(Y)\eta_i(Z)]. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, again using the first equation in (12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d\eta_i(\varphi_i Y, X)\eta_i(Z) - d\eta_i(\varphi_i Z, X)\eta_i(Y) &= \\ &= -2\delta(\eta_j \wedge \eta_k)(\varphi_i Y, X)\eta_i(Z) + 2\delta(\eta_j \wedge \eta_k)(\varphi_i Z, X)\eta_i(Y) \\ &= -2\delta \eta_i(Z)[- \eta_k(Y)\eta_k(X) - \eta_j(X)\eta_j(Y)] + 2\delta \eta_i(Y)[- \eta_k(Z)\eta_k(X) - \eta_j(X)\eta_j(Z)]. \end{aligned}$$

Inserting the above computations in (17), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} g((\nabla_X^g \varphi_i)Y, Z) &= 2\delta[\eta_k(X)g(\varphi_j Y, Z) - \eta_j(X)g(\varphi_k Y, Z)] \\ &\quad - \delta\eta_i(Z)[\eta_k(Y)\eta_k(X) + \eta_j(X)\eta_j(Y)] + \delta\eta_i(Y)[\eta_k(Z)\eta_k(X) + \eta_j(X)\eta_j(Z)] \end{aligned}$$

which implies (14). As regards the proof (15), applying (14) for $Y = \xi_i$, we get

$$(\nabla_X^g \varphi_i)\xi_i = -\delta(\eta_j(X)\xi_j + \eta_k(X)\xi_k).$$

Applying φ_i on both hand-sides, we obtain (15). Equations (16) are immediate consequences of (15). Furthermore, we also get

$$g(\nabla_X^g \xi_i, Y) = -\delta(\eta_j \wedge \eta_k)(X, Y)$$

for every $X, Y \in \mathfrak{X}(M)$. Since $\nabla^g \xi_i$ is skew-symmetric, ξ_i is Killing. \square

Corollary 1. *Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold. Then for every even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$ we have*

$$\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i} \varphi_i = 0, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\xi_i} \varphi_j = -\mathcal{L}_{\xi_j} \varphi_i = 2\delta\varphi_k. \tag{18}$$

Proof. For the first Lie derivative, notice that by (14) we have $\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_i = 0$. Then, applying also (15), for every vector field X we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i} \varphi_i)X &= (\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_i)X - \nabla_{\varphi_i X}^g \xi_i + \varphi_i(\nabla_X^g \xi_i) \\ &= -\delta(\eta_k(\varphi_i X)\xi_j - \eta_j(\varphi_i X)\xi_k) + \delta(\eta_k(X)\varphi_i \xi_j - \eta_j(X)\varphi_i \xi_k) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Now, using (14) for the covariant derivative $\nabla^g \varphi_j$, for every vector field Y , we have

$$(\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_j)Y = 2\delta \varphi_k Y - \delta(\eta_i(Y)\xi_j - \eta_j(Y)\xi_i).$$

Therefore, applying also (15), we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i} \varphi_j)X &= (\nabla_{\xi_i}^g \varphi_j)X - \nabla_{\varphi_j X}^g \xi_i + \varphi_j(\nabla_X^g \xi_i) \\ &= 2\delta \varphi_k X - \delta(\eta_i(X)\xi_j - \eta_j(X)\xi_i) - \delta \eta_k(\varphi_j X)\xi_j - \delta \eta_j(X)\varphi_j \xi_k \\ &= 2\delta \varphi_k X. \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, $\mathcal{L}_{\xi_j} \varphi_i = -2\delta \varphi_k$. \square

Theorem 3. *Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold. Then both the horizontal and the vertical distribution are integrable with totally geodesic leaves. Each leaf of the vertical distribution is locally isomorphic to the Lie group $SO(3)$, with constant sectional curvature δ^2 ; each leaf of the horizontal distribution is endowed with a hyper-Kähler structure. Consequently, the Riemannian Ricci tensor of M is given by*

$$Ric^g = 2\delta^2 \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \otimes \eta_i. \tag{19}$$

Proof. We already know that the horizontal distribution \mathcal{H} is integrable. From (15), for every $X, Y \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H})$ and $i = 1, 2, 3$, we have

$$g(\nabla_X^g Y, \xi_i) = -g(\nabla_X^g \xi_i, Y) = 0,$$

so that the distribution \mathcal{H} has totally geodesic leaves. Furthermore, Equation (16) implies that the vertical distribution \mathcal{V} is also integrable with totally geodesic leaves. In particular $[\xi_i, \xi_j] = 2\delta \xi_k$ for an even permutation (i, j, k) of $(1, 2, 3)$, so that the leaves of \mathcal{V} are locally isomorphic to the Lie group $SO(3)$ and have constant sectional curvature δ^2 . On each leaf of the horizontal distribution \mathcal{H} one can consider the almost hyper-Hermitian structure defined by $(J_i := \varphi_i|_{\mathcal{H}}, g)$, which turns out to be hyper-Kähler due to (14). Consequently, M is locally the Riemannian product of 3-dimensional sphere of curvature δ^2 and a $4n$ -dimensional manifold M' , which is endowed with a hyper-Kähler structure. Since any hyper-Kähler manifold is Ricci flat, we obtain that the Riemannian Ricci tensor of M is given by (19). \square

Remark 3. *From Theorem 3 it follows that any 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold is locally isometric to the Riemannian product of 3-dimensional sphere and a $4n$ -dimensional manifold M' , which is endowed with a hyper-Kähler structure. We recall that 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds are also locally isometric to the Riemannian product of a 3-dimensional sphere of constant curvature δ^2 and a hyper-Kähler manifold. Nevertheless, there is a difference between the two geometries. Looking at the transverse geometry of the foliation defined by the vertical distribution \mathcal{V} , in both cases the Riemannian metric g is projectable, being the vector fields $\xi_i, i = 1, 2, 3$, all Killing. In the case of 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds, each tensor field φ_i is also projectable, as by (11), the Lie derivatives with respect to the Reeb vector fields satisfy $(\mathcal{L}_{\xi_i} \varphi_j)X = 0$ for every $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and for every horizontal vector field X . In the case of 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds, owing to (18), the tensor fields are not projectable. Nevertheless, taking into account the horizontal parts $\Phi_i^{\mathcal{H}} := \Phi_i + \eta_j \wedge \eta_k$ of the fundamental 2-forms Φ_i , one can verify that horizontal 4-form*

$$\Phi_1^{\mathcal{H}} \wedge \Phi_1^{\mathcal{H}} + \Phi_2^{\mathcal{H}} \wedge \Phi_2^{\mathcal{H}} + \Phi_3^{\mathcal{H}} \wedge \Phi_3^{\mathcal{H}}$$

is projectable and defines a transversal quaternionic structure, which turns out to be locally hyper-Kähler.

5. Connections with Totally Skew-Symmetric Torsion

In this section we will show that every 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold is *canonical* in the sense of the definition given in [1], thus admitting a special metric connection with totally skew-symmetric torsion, called canonical. Recall that a metric connection ∇ with torsion T on a Riemannian manifold (M, g) is said to have *totally skew-symmetric torsion*, or *skew torsion* for short, if the (0, 3)-tensor field T defined by $T(X, Y, Z) := g(T(X, Y), Z)$ is a 3-form. The relation between ∇ and the Levi-Civita connection ∇^g is then given by

$$\nabla_X Y = \nabla_X^g Y + \frac{1}{2} T(X, Y).$$

For more details we refer to [20]. We recall now the definition and the characterization of canonical almost 3-contact metric manifolds.

Definition 4 ([1]). An almost 3-contact metric manifold (M, φ_i, ξ_i, η_i, g) is called *canonical* if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) each N_{φ_i} is totally skew-symmetric on H,
- (ii) each ξ_i is a Killing vector field,
- (iii) for any X, Y, Z ∈ Γ(H) and any i, j = 1, 2, 3,

$$N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y, Z) - d\Phi_i(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z) = N_{\varphi_j}(X, Y, Z) - d\Phi_j(\varphi_j X, \varphi_j Y, \varphi_j Z),$$

- (iv) M admits a Reeb Killing function β ∈ C[∞](M), that is the tensor fields A_{ij} defined on H by

$$A_{ij}(X, Y) := g((\mathcal{L}_{\xi_j} \varphi_i)X, Y) + d\eta_j(X, \varphi_i Y) + d\eta_j(\varphi_i X, Y),$$

satisfy

$$A_{ii}(X, Y) = 0, \quad A_{ij}(X, Y) = -A_{ji}(X, Y) = \beta \Phi_k(X, Y),$$

for every X, Y ∈ Γ(H) and every even permutation (i, j, k) of (1, 2, 3).

Here N_{φ_i} also denotes the (0, 3)-tensor field defined by $N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y, Z) := g(N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y), Z)$ and we say that N_{φ_i} is totally skew-symmetric on H if the (0, 3)-tensor is a 3-form on H.

Theorem 4 ([1]). An almost 3-contact metric manifold (M, φ_i, ξ_i, η_i, g) is canonical, with Reeb Killing function β, if and only if it admits a metric connection ∇ with skew torsion such that

$$\nabla_X \varphi_i = \beta(\eta_k(X) \varphi_j - \eta_j(X) \varphi_k)$$

for every vector field X on M and for every even permutation (i, j, k) of (1, 2, 3). If such a connection ∇ exists, it is unique and its torsion is given by

$$\begin{aligned} T(X, Y, Z) &= N_{\varphi_i}(X, Y, Z) - d\Phi_i(\varphi_i X, \varphi_i Y, \varphi_i Z), \\ T(X, Y, \xi_i) &= d\eta_i(X, Y), \\ T(X, \xi_i, \xi_j) &= -g([\xi_i, \xi_j], X), \\ T(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) &= 2(\beta - \delta), \end{aligned}$$

for every X, Y, Z ∈ Γ(H), and i, j = 1, 2, 3, and where δ is the Reeb commutator function.

The connection ∇ is called the *canonical connection* of M, and also satisfies

$$\nabla_X \xi_i = \beta(\eta_k(X) \xi_j - \eta_j(X) \xi_k), \quad \nabla_X \eta_i = \beta(\eta_k(X) \eta_j - \eta_j(X) \eta_k) \tag{20}$$

for every vector field X on M. Therefore, when β = 0 the canonical connection parallelizes all the structure tensor fields, in which case we call the almost 3-contact metric manifold *parallel*.

Both 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki manifolds and 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds turn out to be canonical. In particular,

Theorem 5 ([1]). *Every 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki manifold is a canonical almost 3-contact metric manifold, with constant Reeb Killing function $\beta = 2(\delta - 2\alpha)$. The torsion T of the canonical connection ∇ is given by*

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \wedge d\eta_i + 8(\delta - \alpha) \eta_{123} = 2\alpha \sum_{i=1}^3 \eta_i \wedge \Phi_i^{\mathcal{H}} + 2(\delta - 4\alpha) \eta_{123}$$

and satisfies $\nabla T = 0$.

We denote by η_{123} the 3-form $\eta_1 \wedge \eta_2 \wedge \eta_3$. From the above theorem, it follows that any 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki manifold is a parallel canonical manifold if and only if $\delta = 2\alpha$, in which case the 3-(α, δ)-Sasaki structure is positive ($\alpha\delta > 0$).

Regarding 3- δ -cosymplectic manifolds, we have:

Proposition 5 ([1]). *Any 3- δ -cosymplectic manifold is a parallel canonical almost 3-contact metric manifold. The torsion of the canonical connection is given by*

$$T = -2\delta \eta_{123}.$$

For the class of 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifolds, we have the following

Proposition 6. *Every 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold is a canonical almost 3-contact metric manifold, with constant Reeb Killing function $\beta = 2\delta$. The torsion T of the canonical connection ∇ is given by*

$$T = 2\delta \eta_{123},$$

which satisfies $\nabla T = 0$.

Proof. Let $(M, \varphi_i, \xi_i, \eta_i, g)$ be a 3-(0, δ)-Sasaki manifold. We showed that the structure is hypernormal and the Reeb vector fields are Killing. Furthermore, by the second equation in (12), $d\Phi_i(X, Y, Z) = 0$ for every $X, Y, Z \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H})$. Therefore, conditions (i), (ii) and (iii) in Definition 4 are easily verified. As regards condition (iv), applying the first equation in (4) and Corollary 1, for every $X, Y \in \Gamma(\mathcal{H})$ we have

$$A_{ii}(X, Y) = 0, \quad A_{ij}(X, Y) = -A_{ji}(X, Y) = 2\delta\Phi_k(X, Y).$$

Hence, the structure is canonical with Reeb commutator function $\beta = 2\delta$. Now, by Theorem 4, taking also into account the fact that the vertical distribution is integrable, the only non-vanishing term of the canonical connection is $T(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3) = 2\delta$, so that $T = 2\delta \eta_{123}$. Although the structure is not parallel when $\delta \neq 0$, the torsion satisfies $\nabla T = 0$, as by (20), the 3-form η_{123} is parallel with respect to ∇ . \square

The above result generalizes the result obtained in [2] for the Lie group described in Example 1 (see also Remark 2).

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

1. Agricola, I.; Dileo, G. Generalizations of 3-Sasakian manifolds and skew torsion. *Adv. Geom.* **2020**, *20*, 331–374. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Andrada, A.; Dileo, G. Odd dimensional counterparts of abelian complex and hypercomplex structures. *arXiv* **2020**, arXiv:2006.16435.

3. Blair, D.E. *Riemannian Geometry of Contact and Symplectic Manifolds*, 2nd ed.; Progress in Mathematics 203; Birkhäuser: Boston, MA, USA, 2010.
4. Cappelletti-Montano, B.; De Nicola, A.; Yudin, I. A survey on cosymplectic geometry. *Rev. Math. Phys.* **2013**, *25*, 1343002. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Boyer, C.; Galicki, C. *Sasakian Geometry*; Oxford Mathematical Monographs; Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 2008.
6. Yano, K.; Ishihara, S.; Konishi, M. Normality of almost contact 3-structure. *Tôhoku Math. J.* **1973**, *25*, 167–175. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Cappelletti-Montano, B.; De Nicola, A.; Yudin, I. Cosymplectic p -spheres. *J. Geom. Phys.* **2016**, *100*, 68–79. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Kuo, Y.-Y. On almost contact 3-structure. *Tôhoku Math. J.* **1970**, *22*, 325–332. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Boyer, C.P.; Galicki, K. 3-Sasakian manifolds. In *Surveys in Differential Geometry: Essays on Einstein Manifolds*; Wang, M., Lebrun, C., Eds.; International Press: Cambridge, UK, 2007; pp. 123–184.
10. Boyer, C.P.; Galicki, K.; Mann, B.M. The geometry and the topology of 3-Sasakian manifolds. *J. Reine Angew. Math.* **1994**, *455*, 183–220.
11. Cappelletti-Montano, B. De Nicola, A. 3-Sasakian manifolds, 3-cosymplectic manifolds and Darboux theorem. *J. Geom. Phys.* **2007**, *57*, 2509–2520. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Cappelletti-Montano, B.; De Nicola, A.; Yudin, I. Topology of 3-cosymplectic manifolds. *Q. J. Math.* **2013**, *64*, 59–82. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Cappelletti-Montano, B.; De Nicola, A.; Dileo, G. 3-quasi-Sasakian manifolds. *Ann. Glob. Anal. Geom.* **2008**, *33*, 397–409. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Cappelletti-Montano, B.; De Nicola, A.; Dileo, G. The geometry of 3-quasi-Sasakian manifolds. *Int. J. Math.* **2009**, *20*, 1081–1105. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Kashiwada, T. On a contact 3-structure. *Math. Z.* **2001**, *238*, 829–832. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Pastore, A.M.; Falcitelli, M.; Ianus, S. *Riemannian Submersions and Related Topics*; World Scientific Publishing Co., Inc.: River Edge, NJ, USA, 2004.
17. Agricola, I.; Dileo, G.; Stecker, L. Homogeneous non-degenerate 3- (α, δ) -Sasaki manifolds and submersions over quaternionic Kähler spaces. *arXiv* **2020**, arXiv:2011.13434.
18. Konishi, M. On manifolds with Sasakian 3-structure over quaternion Kaehler manifolds. *Kodai Math. Semin. Rep.* **1975**, *26*, 194–200. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Tanno, S. Remarks on a triple of K -contact structures. *Tôhoku Math. J. II. Ser.* **1996**, *48*, 519–531. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Agricola, I. The Srní lectures on non-integrable geometries with torsion. *Arch. Math. (Brno)* **2006**, *42*, 5–84.